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TOURIST SOUVENIRS IN DESTINATION BRANDING (CASE STUDY OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARELIA)

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Abstract. The article focuses on the role of souvenir products and their development within the tourism industry of the Republic of Karelia. It examines the main types, functions, and the role of souvenirs in strengthening the brand of tour and excursion companies, as well as the primary categories of souvenirs offered in the region. Special attention is given to the significance of souvenirs as a tool for promoting the region, preserving cultural heritage, supporting local producers, and contributing to the country's economic development. Popular excursions to local enterprises and workshops are described, allowing tourists to explore the process of creating souvenirs and participate in it, thereby maintaining a connection with the visited destination. Modern trends such as personalization, functionality, eco-friendliness of souvenirs, and their impact on strengthening the brand of tour companies are highlighted. The article is based on an analysis of literature, statistical data, and practical examples, making it valuable for researchers, tour operators, and anyone interested in the development of tourism in Karelia.

Keywords: souvenir products, Republic of Karelia, tourism, traditional crafts, excursions, workshops, cultural heritage, branding, economic development

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СУВЕНИРНАЯ ПРОДУКЦИЯ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ РАЗВИТИЯ ТУРИСТСКИХ ДЕСТИНАЦИЙ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРЕЛИЯ)

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Аннотация. Статья посвящена роли сувенирной продукции и ее развитию на примере туристской индустрии Республики Карелия. Рассмотрены основные виды, функции, роль в развитии бренда туристско-экскурсионных фирм, также рассмотрены основные виды и категории сувениров, предлагаемых в республике Карелии. Особое внимание уделено значению сувениров как инструмента продвижения региона, сохранения культурного наследия и поддержки местных производителей и развития экономики страны. Описаны популярные экскурсии на предприятия и мастер-классы, позволяющие туристам познакомиться с процессом создания сувениров и принять в нем участие, сохранив связь с местом, которое посетил турист. Подчеркнуты современные тенденции, такие как персонализация, функциональность сувениров, экологичность, а также их влияние на укрепление бренда туристско-экскурсионных фирм. Статья основана на анализе литературы, статистических данных и практических примеров, что делает ее полезной для исследователей, туроператоров и всех, кто интересуется развитием туризма в Карелии.

Ключевые слова: сувенирная продукция, Республика Карелия, туризм, традиционные ремесла, экскурсии, мастер-классы, культурное наследие, экологичность, брендинг, экономическое развитие, персонализация, цифровизация

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Introduction.

Souvenir products are becoming an important component of a territory's resource potential, as they often reflect the unique characteristics of a destination and help materialize the emotions and impressions gained from a trip. The production of souvenirs enables local residents to participate in the creation of the regional tourism product, positively impacting the well-being of local communities and small businesses. However, many destinations suffer from an abundance of «faceless» souvenirs that do not serve a resourceful or stimulating function but merely provide short-term income for vendors.

As a result, increasing attention is being given to souvenir products by authorities, businesses, and the scientific community. The development of souvenirs is a complex and responsible process that should involve representatives of the destination's tourism industry, designers, local manufacturers, experts in regional studies, and other stakeholders in the tourism market.

The aim of this article is to examine the phenomenon of souvenir products as a driver of tourism development and their significance in regional tourism growth, using one of the most attractive destinations in Russia—the Republic of Karelia—as a case study.

Research Methods. The article employs conceptual principles of the systems approach, as well as methods of deduction, logical analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, and graphical interpretation of data.

Research and Discussion.

A review of scientific literature indicates that, until recently, significant attention has been given to souvenirs as a tool of museum communication [12,16]. To remain competitive, museums need to develop special offers that can not only attract attention but also serve as a means of engagement with the audience. This can be achieved through the release of exclusive souvenirs that, on the one hand, convey the spirit of museum exhibits, and on the other, help bridge the gap between historical heritage and the current generation.

Souvenir products play several key roles in museum communication. First, they serve as tangible carriers of information about the museum, its exhibitions, and its cultural mission. Second, souvenirs serve as a powerful emotional link, connecting visitors to the museum experience by creating a tangible «bridge» between historical heritage and contemporary life. Third, they function as organic marketing tools—when

visitors share or display their purchased souvenirs, they spark conversations that can draw new visitors to the institution.

A critical factor in developing museum souvenirs is ensuring their distinctiveness and cultural authenticity. Today's museumgoers actively seek out keepsakes that are not only thematically tied to the institution's collections but also exhibit artistic merit. Such items may include faithful reproductions of artifacts, designs inspired by permanent exhibits, or creative interpretations of historical narratives. For instance, souvenirs crafted using traditional methods or modeled after heritage artworks enable visitors to physically engage with cultural history, effectively taking a fragment of the museum's legacy home with them [12].

Furthermore, modern museum merchandising increasingly prioritizes environmental consciousness. Many institutions now incorporate sustainable practices by opting for biodegradable materials, upcycled components, and locally sourced production—a shift that reflects both global ecological movements and the museum's commitment to ethical operations.

In particular, souvenirs with personalized elements—such as the visitor's name, the date of their visit, or special inscriptions—not only become more meaningful to the buyer but also strengthen their emotional connection to the museum. Such products play a key role in audience engagement: they serve not just as a marketing tool but also as a means of conveying cultural values [16].

Souvenir products are studied in the context of a region's marketing strategy and as an element of territorial branding, as souvenirs serve as carriers of regional tourism brands [9].

In the work of O.E. Afanasyeva [2], souvenirs are considered as part of the experience economy, as well as a mechanism for perceiving space, allowing tourists to immerse themselves more deeply in the theme of a destination.

Another aspect of studying regional souvenir products is their role in shaping the image of a region [15]. Souvenirs function not only as material objects but also as crucial tools for enhancing a region's tourism appeal. They become symbols associated with a specific territory, its culture, history, and traditions. In her article, Y.V. Bodrova highlights that souvenirs help create a lasting image of a region in tourists' minds, reinforcing its uniqueness and recognizability [5]. The author emphasizes that

souvenir products should reflect the key characteristics of a region, such as its natural wealth, historical events, traditional crafts, and cultural symbols. These souvenirs not only preserve memories of a visit but also contribute to the region's promotion, as tourists take them home and, in doing so, become «ambassadors» of the region, spreading awareness and learning more about the history of traditional crafts that have been «lost» in modern times.

Furthermore, Y.V. Bodrova stresses that souvenir products should be of high quality, functional, and aesthetically appealing to meet the expectations of modern tourists [5]. This is especially important in the competitive landscape, where regions vie for tourist attention. Unique and original souvenirs, created with modern trends in mind—such as sustainability and personalization—can significantly enhance a region's attractiveness. Souvenirs effectively promote the region by boosting its tourist appeal and creating an emotional connection with travelers, which enhances the area's recognition.

Souvenir products, while possessing significant promotional potential, require comprehensive study. For example, in the study by N.P. Avilova [1], a classification of souvenir products is proposed, along with an analysis of modern tourists' demand for unique souvenir attributes. The authors identify both the strengths and weaknesses of different types of souvenirs based on tourist perceptions and experiences.

Thus, the large number of scientific studies on souvenir products in tourism highlights the relevance of this research topic. On the one hand, the importance of this issue is evident, but on the other hand, it remains insufficiently explored. At the same time, souvenirs from Karelia are rarely reflected in scientific publications.

T.Y. Bystrova and A.K. Khimatullin define a souvenir as «an object of nature or culture that holds a heightened degree of spiritual closeness to a person» [6]. In other words, a souvenir is associated with a memory or a regional (destination) association, and its main function is to remind its owner not only of a particular region, object, or significant event but also of the emotions connected to them.

Scientific publications also present regional case studies and practices, as well as descriptions of technologies for creating various types of souvenir products [18,21].

Attempts to classify souvenirs have been made repeatedly. The most successful approach to the classification of souvenir products is presented in the work of T.Y. Bystrova and A.K. Khimatullin [6]:

- By theme (associations with a specific place, personality, event, date, etc.);
- By purpose (utilitarian, decorative, etc.);
- By type of material used (wood, turquoise, fabric, paper, metal, etc.);
- By industry affiliation (souvenirs of artistic crafts, food industry, printing industry, etc.).

Based on the results of the annual All-Russian Tourist Souvenir Contest, which has been held since 2015 at the initiative of Gennady Shatalov, Chairman of the Board of the Region PR Public Relations Development Fund (FROS Region PR)¹, thousands of souvenir product designs from most regions of Russia are submitted each year. As a result of this competition, a book-guide on creating unique souvenirs as a tool for territorial development was published [22]. Table 1 does not include the contest categories such as «City Souvenir», «Museum Souvenir», etc., without an analysis of pricing for different souvenir categories.

As shown by the statistical data presented in Fig. 1, special attention is given to various types of gastronomic souvenirs. This is due to the fact that tourists actively purchase regional and local gastronomic products, and local gastronomic brands have proven their effectiveness as factors in attracting visitors.

An analysis of scientific literature and existing practices has allowed us to identify key trends in the changing properties of modern souvenirs:

- Functionality: tourists prefer souvenirs that can be used in everyday life.
- Personalization: enhances a souvenir's value by adding unique elements such as a name, date, or commemorative inscription.
- Support for local producers: souvenirs created by local artisans are becoming increasingly in demand.
- Digitalization: virtual souvenirs, such as digital postcards, are also becoming more popular.

Souvenirs are actively involved in the tourism process at all its stages (Fig. 2).

Based on the studied properties of souvenirs, let's consider them in relation to the Republic of Karelia. Managers of tourist and excursion firms, as well

¹ Shatalov, G. V. – Chairman of the Board of the Region PR Public Relations Development Fund. His organization focuses on promoting regional initiatives and projects aimed at developing public relations, including tourism and cultural exchange between regions of Russia and foreign countries.

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Table 1. Distribution of Winners in the «Tourist Souvenir» Competition.

Category of Souvenirs	% of Total Winners
Gastronomic Souvenirs (food, drinks, sweets, dry mixes, etc.)	45
Household Items (candlesticks, candles, mugs, plates, saucers, etc.)	20
Jewelry (bracelets, necklaces, earrings, etc.)	10
Accessories (bags, wallets, keychains, etc.)	5
Cosmetics (creams, soap, aromatic candles, etc.)	5
Art Objects (figurines, paintings, miniatures, etc.)	4
Clothing (T-shirts, scarves, hats with regional symbols)	3
Games (board games, puzzles, etc.)	2
Dolls (traditional, souvenir)	1
Printed Products (books, guides)	1
Magnets	1
Pins, Commemorative Coins, Souvenir Signs	1
Special Ethnographic Souvenirs (amulets, dream catchers, charms, etc.)	2

as tour guides, should be particularly knowledgeable about the most characteristic souvenirs of their region to use them in tourism processes and for tourism purposes. An analysis of the assortment of souvenir products sold in souvenir shops, art salons, tourist information centers (TIC), museums, bookstores, art galleries, exhibitions, and grocery stores has shown that the souvenir market in the Republic of Karelia

offers both souvenirs of folk crafts and souvenirs from various industries.

Folk art in Karelia has a rich history and is deeply rooted in the culture of the region. One of the prominent elements is traditional wood carving, which often adorns household items and architecture. Another well-known form is textile art, including embroidery and weaving. Karelia's birch bark and bone products

Figure 1. Distribution of Winners in the «Tourist Souvenir» Competition.

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Fig. 2. Use and Significance of Souvenirs at Different Stages of a Tourist Trip

testify to the craftsmanship of local artisans. Music and dance, such as the «kantele,» reflect the rich spiritual tradition of the people.

In recent years, tourism in Karelia has received particular attention in the Priladozhsky district. This region has become popular among tourists due to its picturesque landscapes, historical sites, and cultural traditions. Souvenir workshops are actively developing in the Priladozhsky district, producing items that reflect local traditions and culture. Masters create unique souvenirs, such as wood carving, birch bark products, and other folk crafts. As a result, the region has attracted not only tourists but also investors' interest, which contributes to the development of the local economy.

The most famous folk craft of the Republic of Karelia is wood carving (Karelian carving). Carving masters from Karelia are renowned for their unique products, which attract attention both in Russia and abroad. Wood carving masters from Karelia have received numerous awards at both Russian and international exhibitions: the All-Russian Exhibition of Folk Arts and Crafts «Ladya,» the International Exhibition «Formula of Handicrafts,» the «Russian Forest» exhibition, and the international festival «Guild

of Masters.» These achievements contribute to the popularization of Karelian folk art and help preserve traditional techniques.

These and similar events undoubtedly contribute to the creation of new and original souvenirs based on traditional folk arts. For instance, a survey conducted by the author among employees of art salons in Karelia and the Priladozhsky district revealed that wood carving is the most popular item among both tourists and those planning a trip who wish to take a Karelian souvenir with them. This is because such products embody the uniqueness and traditions of the region. Birch bark crafts come in second place in terms of popularity due to their lightness and originality.

The third most significant and interesting items for tourists are herbal and berry tinctures, as well as local natural products such as honey and other delicacies (e.g., fish-based products). Natural cosmetics and medicinal ointments are also in high demand. Local producers offer various natural tinctures with unique flavors and aromas, made from Karelian herbs and berries (such as raspberries, blueberries, and lingonberries). Karelian artisans preserve traditional crafts: weaving with vibrant patterns, birch bark weaving, and

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wooden toy making, passing down cultural heritage through generations.

In the souvenir market of the Republic of Karelia, products from the printing industry are widely represented and can be purchased in souvenir shops, tourist information centers (TIC), kiosks, museums, bookstores, art galleries, and exhibitions. Primarily, these include colorful photo albums, pictures, posters, and postcards—artistic reproductions of works by Karelian artists, as well as photographs of beautiful landscapes, paintings depicting Karelia's nature, famous architectural landmarks, and traditional patterns.

Sets of postcards also fall under the category of printed souvenirs. This type of souvenir product is attractive due to its relatively low price, making it popular among tourists with limited budgets.

In Russia, the first postcards featuring city views appeared in 1895, when postcards depicting Moscow streets were issued [11]. By the end of the 19th century, the first postcards in the Republic of Karelia were published [17]. One of the first artists to create such postcards was Alexander Benois [3], whose works played a pivotal role in popularizing Karelian landscapes and cultural heritage. Printed in prestigious capital-city typographies, these postcards stood out for their high-quality production and wide distribution, shaping the region's tourist image. During the Soviet era, although Karelia never became a mass tourism hub, it was actively promoted through postcard products featuring local landmarks, nature, and cities like Petrozavodsk. Of particular practical value was the inclusion of multilingual text, which expanded the souvenir market's reach to international visitors.

Karelia has successfully developed a line of musical souvenirs, including the compilation «Music of Karelia» (2006) featuring traditional melodies. Local edible souvenirs showcase berry jams from «*Karelian Yagodka*», smoked fish, and canned goods from the «*Kalevala*» brand, all packaged in ethnic-style designs. Particularly popular are Karelian pies with traditional fillings, decorated in folk-art style. These products blend authentic flavors with the region's cultural identity.

The Republic of Karelia boasts a distinctive array of traditional alcoholic beverages that serve as popular tourists keepsakes. Regional manufacturers like the historic Petrozavodsk liquor plant and the renowned «Kizhi» label produce authentic drinks incorporating indigenous ingredients such as Arctic berries and forest botanicals. Among the most sought-after varieties

are fruit-based liqueurs featuring cranberries and rowanberries, as well as conifer-flavored spirits, including limited-edition craft batches from local producers. This specialty market segment demonstrates ongoing innovation in its product offerings.

However, despite these promising developments, the current souvenir selection doesn't fully capitalize on its potential to enhance the region's tourism appeal. Many available products fail to adequately represent or promote Karelia's unique cultural identity to visitors. Therefore, we conducted a study on the use of souvenirs in tourism in Karelia.

According to M.B. Birzhakov, purchasing souvenirs is one of the goals of a tourist trip, and not the least important one at that [4; 52]. Therefore, a region hosting tourists should offer them a wide range of souvenirs, and tour companies should take this into account in their programs.

Many tour companies in regions such as «Karelia Tour,» «Tours to Karelia,» «Karelian Expanses,» «Northern Wind,» and others, for the convenience of their clients, bring tourists to specialized souvenir shops on tour buses and allocate specific time for this purpose. In these souvenir shops, consultants, understanding the time constraints of tourists, help them select products and souvenirs according to their requests and budget. Marketing research in Karelia helps identify tourist preferences: Europeans favor wooden crafts, natural food products, and fish delicacies; Americans prefer nature-inspired souvenirs like shungite; while Chinese tourists tend to choose traditional Russian nesting dolls and magnets. These insights are valuable for developing the souvenir market and enhancing tour guide services.

Since a souvenir reflects the cultural achievements of a region and conveys national and local flavor, it is used as a tool for marketing and promoting the region [10, 204]. Souvenirs become important elements of the tourist experience, allowing urban residents and tourists to deepen their knowledge of local culture and traditions, support local artisans and producers, keep memorable items that reflect the uniqueness of the region, and spread information about the destination among friends and acquaintances, thereby generating additional interest in the region.

«Centers of Folk Art and Cultural Initiatives» in various regions attract tourists as sites for excursions and souvenir shopping. Some Russian tour companies organize visits to enterprises and workshops producing

souvenir products. In Karelia, there are excursions to workshops where tourists can observe the process of shungite processing and purchase finished products. One of the well-known and large workshops is the *Shungite Workshop in Petrozavodsk*, which offers tours and masterclasses on creating shungite jewelry. Workshops for processing wood and birch bark, where tourists can observe the process of creating traditional souvenirs, include the «Karelian Birch Bark Workshop,» where baskets, wooden boxes, decorations, and other items are made from birch bark (they offer workshops on weaving).

Another interesting excursion with a master class takes place in the wooden workshops in the village of Kinerma, where tourists can see how carved figurines and wooden products are created, and the artisans will offer the chance to create a small piece to take home as a souvenir. The «Ceramic Workshop in Petrozavodsk» offers excursions and master classes on ceramic painting. Textile workshops include the Textile Workshop in Sortavala, where tourists can observe the process of creating woven products and take part in master classes. The reception of tourists at the workshop is carefully thought out, making the visit one of the most memorable and vivid moments of the excursion.

Recently, many tourists are interested in excursions that include visits to factories producing Karelian balms, tinctures, and vodka products. One such factory is «Karelian Tinctures,» where tourists can learn about the production process of tinctures and balms and taste the products.

To enhance tourist destinations through souvenir products, we propose a comprehensive strategy. First, creating exclusive 'ambassador' souvenirs available at production sites with opportunities to observe the crafting process.

Second, each souvenir should carry a distinctive story rooted in local traditions to enhance its value. Specialized collector's items-such as those linked to UNESCO World Heritage sites-could cater to niche markets. Equally important is curating cohesive souvenir lines that embody the region's identity through traditional motifs and materials. Organizing competitions for local artisans would spur innovation while preserving crafts, ensuring high-quality, unique products.

Additionally, establishing a «Crafts Street» in a historic area of Karelia could house mini-workshops for traditional crafts. This space would offer tours, workshops, and sales of heritage-based souvenirs, boosting tourism appeal and regional economic growth.

For example, in 2020, the number of tourists was 840 thousand, and by 2024, this number had increased to around 1.7 million¹.

For souvenirs to effectively promote destinations, they must balance uniqueness, cultural relevance, and affordability. A holistic strategy encompassing exclusive designs, compelling narratives, targeted collections, and artisan support-is key to advancing the industry.

Excursions to factories and workshops for creating souvenirs are becoming a popular format of tourism, allowing tourists to immerse themselves more deeply in the culture of the destination (region).

References

1. Avilova, N. L., Skabeeva, L. I., Churilina, I. N., & Nekhaichuk, D. V. (2023). Souvenir products as a factor in the development of tourist destinations. *Contemporary Issues in Service and Tourism*, 2, 21–31. URL: (Accessed: 22.02.2025). (In Russ.).
2. Afanasyev, O. E., & Afanasyeva, A. V. (2019). Tourist legends as a component of the experience economy and the process of forming travel experiences. *Contemporary Issues in Service and Tourism*, 13(2), 7–20. (In Russ.).
3. Benoit, A. N. (1923). *Memories of Karelia*. Petrograd: Academy of Sciences Press. (In Russ.).
4. Birzhakov, M. B. (2002). *Introduction to Tourism* (4th ed., revised and expanded). St. Petersburg: Gerda Publishing House. (In Russ.).
5. Bodrova, Y. V. (2019). Souvenir products as a tool for forming tourist attractiveness. *Service and Tourism – Innovative Development*, 65–68. (In Russ.).
6. Bystronova, T. Yu., & Khismatulin, A. K. (2009). *Souvenir: It's Serious: A Social and Communicative Analysis of Souvenirs*. Yekaterinburg: Advertising Studio «ra4.ru». (In Russ.).
7. Volkov, S. K. (2021). Tourism as a sector of the creative economy. *Creative Economy*, 15(5), 2153–2162. (In Russ.).

¹ Rosstat: website of the Federal State Statistics Service. URL: <https://rosstat.gov.ru/> (Accessed: 10.03.2025).

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8. Voskoloivich, N. A. (2024). On the way to digital development. *State Management. Electronic Bulletin*, 102. Moscow: Economics Faculty, Lomonosov Moscow State University. (In Russ.).
9. Dashkova, E. V., & Ivushkina, E. B. (2020). Souvenir products as a tool for promoting a tourist destination. *Global and Regional Aspects of Sustainable Development: Current Realities*, 224–229. (In Russ.).
10. Kleiman, A. A., & Evreinov, O. B. (2015). *Tourism Infrastructure: Development Strategy (Textbook)*. Moscow: NTC INFRA-M. (In Russ.).
11. Kovalenko, A. A. (1988). *The History of Postcards in Russia*. Moscow: Iskusstvo. (In Russ.).
12. Krivosheeva, T. M. (2016). Souvenir products in museums as a tool for emotional communication with visitors. *Contemporary Issues in Service and Tourism*, 10(2), 29–37. (In Russ.).
13. Mikhaylova, A. V., & Shkurko, N. S. (2023). The role of creative spaces and creative tourism in the regions of the Russian Federation for the formation of a creative sphere. *Creative Economy*, 8, 2873–2886. (In Russ.).
14. Molchanova, V. A. (2017). Trends in innovative development of tourist destinations: «smart destination». *Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 9–3, 715–720. (In Russ.).
15. Nikitina, D. Yu. (2016). Souvenir products as a means of strengthening the image of a tourist destination. *Economics and Society*, 2(21). URL: (Accessed: 22.02.2025). (In Russ.).
16. Nikiforova, A. A., & Skulmovskaya, L. G. (2018). Souvenir products in museums: Modern case practices. *Herald of Culture and Arts*, 2(54), 80–88. (In Russ.).
17. Petrova, L. V. (1996). *Karelia in Postcards of the Early 20th Century*. St. Petersburg: Petropolis. (In Russ.).
18. Pushin, N. S. (2018). Souvenir products as a means of territorial marketing. *Problems, Experience, and Perspectives in the Development of Tourism, Service, and Socio-Cultural Activities in Russia and Abroad*, 82–85. (In Russ.).
19. Serdyukov, S. D., Romanova, G. M., & Serdyukova, N. K. (2022). *Information Support and Promotion of a Tourist Destination in the Context of Digital Transformation (Textbook)*. Moscow: First Economic Publishing House, 150–157. (In Russ.).
20. Sidorina, T. V. (2015). Trends in the development of the souvenir sphere in tourism. *Problems and Perspectives in the Development of Light Industry and the Service Sector*, 95. (In Russ.).
21. Zhang, C. (2022). *Research on the creative strategy of souvenir product design for cultural tourism: A case study of the intangible cultural heritage of the Hulunbuir region in China*. (Doctoral dissertation, Moscow). (In Russ.).
22. Shatalov, G., & Kosykh, V. (2024). *Tourist Souvenir: From Idea to Tourist*. St. Petersburg: Peter. (In Russ.).
23. Khatrii, I. (2019). Information Technology in Tourism & Hospitality: A Review of Ten Years of Publications. *Journal of Tourism & Hospitality Education*, 9, 70–88.